

Conditions to preserve sedimentary record of channel planforms in temperate rivers of the Northern HemisphereMarcin Słowik¹, József Dezső², János Kovács^{3,4}, Mariusz Galka⁵, Györgyi Sipos⁶

¹ Adam Mickiewicz University, Institute of Geology, Geohazards Research Unit, ul. B. Krygowskiego 12, 61-680 Poznań, Poland - corresponding author: slowikgeo@poczta.onet.pl

² University of Pécs, Institute of Geography and Earth Sciences, Department of Environmental and Physical Geography, Ifjúság u. 6, H-7624 Pécs, Hungary

³ University of Pécs, Department of Geology and Meteorology, Ifjúság u. 6, H-7624 Pécs, Hungary

⁴ University of Pécs, Szentágotthai Research Centre, Environmental Analytical and Geoanalytical Research Group, Ifjúság u. 20, H-7624 Pécs, Hungary

⁵ University of Lodz, Faculty of Biology and Environmental Protection, Department of Biogeography, Paleoeecology and Nature Conservation, 1/3 Banacha Str., 90-237 Lodz, Poland

⁶ University of Szeged, Department of Geoinformatics, Physical and Environmental Geography, Egyetem u. 2, 6722 Szeged, Hungary

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Introduction

This supplemental material contains three figures and four tables. The figures show an example of a GPR (ground-penetrating radar) image showing how hydraulic radii and cross-sectional areas were estimated for the former channels (fig.S1), GPR images showing the internal structure of anabranching channels and floodplains of the middle Odra (Poland) and Sió Valleys (Hungary) (fig.S2), and aerial images of the South Saskatchewan River (Canada) (fig.S3). The tables show data describing the geometry of channels preserved in ancient rock records (Table S1), results of a statistical test applied to verify whether the values of sinuosities of channels preserved in the top parts of the modern floodplains are statistically different from sinuosities of channels preserved in ancient fluvial records (Table S2), values of manning n coefficients and standard errors (Table S3), estimations of palaeodischarges and standard errors (Tables S4). Data regarding channel geometry, age of former channels, values of Manning hydraulic roughness coefficients, and palaeodischarges were created by Słowik (2013, 2014), and Słowik et al. (2020, 2021). Information about how the values of roughness coefficients, palaeodischarges, and channel belt widths were estimated, and uncertainties of the estimations, are shown in the main body of our paper.

Figure S1. Example of GPR section used for the estimation of hydraulic radius and cross-sectional area.

Figure S2. Internal structure of anabranching channel fills and floodplains of the middle Obra and Sió Rivers.

Figure S3. South Saskatchewan River (Canada) with braided planform occupying the whole valley width near Outlook, and palaeomeanders preserved along the edge of the valley south of Saskatoon.

Table S1. Channel width, channel belt width, sinuosity and braiding index of selected channel planforms preserved in ancient fluvial records.

Name of river course	Channel planform	channel width (m)	channel belt width (m)	sinuosity braiding index*	age	references
Jurassic Scalby Formation (England)	meandering	N/A	N/A	1.3	Middle Jurassic	McMahon and Davies (2018)
Gulf of Thailand	meandering	450	8630	1.75	Pleistocene	Durkin et al. (2018), Reijnenstein (2011)
Caineville Wash fluvial system (USA)	meandering	30 20 40	N/A N/A N/A	1.58 2.71 1.36	Upper Jurassic	Swan et al. (2018)
Triassic Snadd Formation, Barents Sea (Norway)	meandering anabranching	1400 ~400	N/A N/A	4.13 3-5* 5.01**	Triassic	Swan et al. (2018), Klausen et al. (2014)
Upper Arang Formation, West Natuna Basin (Indonesia)	meandering	100	6600	2.86	Middle Miocene	Yan et al. (2018)
Pattani rift basin (Gulf of Thailand)	meandering	450	9100	1.89	Tertiary	Yan et al. (2018)
Permian Beaufort Group, South Western Karoo (South Africa)	meandering	450	4100	1.63	Permian	Yan et al. (2018)
McMurray Formation (Canada)	meandering	~1000 ~1000 ~1000 ~1000	~40000 ~40000 ~40000 ~40000	5.58 2.28 3.4 1.8	Early Cretaceous	Durkin et al. (2018)
Cedar Mountain Formation (USA)	meandering	~40	660	1.39	Cretaceous	Cardenas et al. (2020)
Meandering channel belt in Mississippi Delta (USA)	meandering	N/A	11500	1.65	Late Miocene	Armstrong et al. (2014)

References

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Cardenas, B.T., Mohrig, D., Goudge, T.A., Hughes, C.M., Levy, J.S., Swanson, T. & Zhao, F. (2018). The anatomy of exhumed river-channel belts: bedform to belt-scale river kinematics of the Ruby Ranch Member, Cretaceous Cedar Mountain Formation, Utah, USA. *Sedimentology*, doi: 10.1111/sed.12765

Durkin, P.R., Hubbard, S.M., Holbrook, J. & Boyd, R. (2018). Evolution of fluvial meander belt deposits and implications for the completeness of the stratigraphic record. *GSA Bulletin*, 130, 721-739.

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Klausen, T.G., Ryseth, A.E., Helland-Hansen, W., Gawthorpe, R. & Laursen, I. (2014). Spatial and temporal changes in geometries of fluvial channel bodies from the Triassic Snadd Formation of offshore Norway. *Journal of Sedimentary Research*, 84, 567-585.

McMahon, W.J. & Davies, N.S. (2018). The shortage of geological evidence for pre-vegetation rivers. In: *Fluvial meanders and their sedimentary products in the rock record* (Eds M. Ghinassi, L. Colombera, N.P. Mountney, A.J.H. Reesink) IAS Special Publ. 48, 119-148, Wiley Blackwell.

Reijnenstein, H.M., Posamentier, H.W. & Bhattacharya, J.P. (2011). Seismic geomorphology and high-resolution seismic stratigraphy of inner-shelf fluvial, estuarine, deltaic and marine sequences, Gulf of Thailand. *AAPG Bull.*, 95, 1959-1990.

Swan, A., Hartley, A.J., Owen, A. & Howell, J. (2018). Reconstruction of a sandy point bar deposit: implications for fluvial facies analysis. In: *Fluvial meanders and their sedimentary products in the rock record* (Eds M. Ghinassi, L. Colombera, N.P. Mountney, A.J.H. Reesink) IAS Special Publ. 48, 445-474, Wiley Blackwell.

Yan, N., Colombera, L., Mountney, N.P., Dorrell, R. (2018). Fluvial point-bar architecture and facies heterogeneity and their influence on intra-bar static connectivity in humid coastal-plain and dryland fan systems. In: *Fluvial meanders and their sedimentary products in the rock record* (Eds M. Ghinassi, L. Colombera, N.P. Mountney, A.J.H. Reesink) IAS Special Publ. 48, 475-508, Wiley Blackwell

Table S2. Data and results of a Welch's t-test conducted to verify the difference between sinuosities of channels preserved in top parts of floodplains and ancient rock record.

sinuosity of channels in top parts of floodplains from Table 1	sinuosity of channels preserved in rock record from Table S1
1,86	1,3
3,03	1,75
1,23	1,58
1,2	2,71
1,27	1,36
1,23	4,13
1,58	2,86
1,47	1,89
2,75	1,63
3,37	5,58
2,44	2,28
2,44	3,4
1,66	1,8
2,68	1,39
1,64	1,65

sinuosity of channels in top parts of floodplains from Table 1	sinuosity of channels preserved in rock record from Table S1
mean: 2,27	mean: 2,35
Standard deviation: 1,01	Standard deviation: 1,21

Tested hypothesis:

H0: sinuosity of channels preserved in top parts of floodplains is not statistically different from sinuosity of channels in ancient rock record

3,4
1,21
2,21
3,75
1,4
1,35
1,4
1,92
2,32
3
3,57
1,87
2,14
1,75
2,25
2,3
2,9
1,72
1,83
2,11
1,96
4,3
2,7
3,46
1,51
2,45
2,45
2,45
2,48
2,48
2,48
1,79
1,79
3,63
2,7
1,32
1,54
1,62
7,59
2,37
2,04
1,5
1,7
1,59
3,16
1,48
1,81

The screenshot shows the GraphPad Prism website interface. The main heading is "Welch t test results". Below this, it provides the following information:

- P value and statistical significance:** The two-tailed P value equals 0,5687. By conventional criteria, this difference is considered to be not statistically significant.
- Confidence interval:** The mean of Recent channel planforms minus Ancient channel planforms equals -3,6096. 95% confidence interval of this difference: From -16,3090 to 9,0899.
- Intermediate values used in calculations:** t = 0,5749, df = 39, standard error of difference = 6,278.
- Learn more:** GraphPad's web site includes portions of the manual for GraphPad Prism that can help you learn statistics. First, review the meaning of [P values](#) and [confidence intervals](#). Then learn how to interpret results from an [unpaired or paired t test](#). These links include GraphPad's popular [analysis checklists](#).
- Review your data:**

Group	Recent channel planforms	Ancient channel planforms
Mean	21,2284	24,8379
SD	27,6069	31,0161
SEM	2,4984	5,7595
N	122	29

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Table S3. Estimated values of Manning hydraulic roughness coefficients.

Obra River valley (Poland) (Stowik et al., 2020)

Large-scale meanders (14650 - 11200 cal. BP)

SE (standard error)

		N Manning	min	mean	max
n1: surface roughness: (caused by grain size of sediments at channel bottom)	0.19 mm	0.012	0.012	0.012	0.012
n2: effect of vegetation small (Late Glacial channels with sparse vegetation)		0.002-0.01	0.002	0.006	0.01
n3: channel irregularity (bars, dunes, ripplemarks) minor (no or rare traces of bedforms in the channel fills)		0.001-0.005	0.001	0.003	0.005
n4: channel alignment gradual variations in channel cross-sections (a regular meandering planform with similar widths and depths of channels)		0	0	0	0
n5: effect of obstructions negligible (a few scattered obstructions: situation possible in the Late Glacial with tundra or park vegetation with potentially few tree stumps in river bed)		0-0.004	0	0.002	0.004
		Total	0.015	0.023	0.031
m: effect of channel meandering severe	2.32 sinuosity:		1.3	1.3	1.3

Manning n coefficient:

min	mean	max
0.0195	0.0299	0.0403

0.0060

Anabranching channels (10700 - 200 cal. BP)

		N Manning	min	mean	max
n1: surface roughness:	0.2 mm	0.012	0.012	0.012	0.012
n2: effect of vegetation medium (the presence of vegetation in the channels is possible, however, there are traces of eroding and reworking of the channels' bottom)		0.01-0.025	0.01	0.0175	0.025
n3: channel irregularity (bars, dunes, ripplemarks) moderate (traces of bedforms and bars in channel fills)		0.006-0.01	0.006	0.008	0.01
n4: channel alignment large and small cross-sections alternating occasionally The main flow shifts occasionally owing to changes in cross-sectional shape		0.001-0.005	0.001	0.003	0.005
n5: effect of obstructions appreciable (traces of buried objects, possibly buried tree logs, in the channel fills)		0.02-0.03	0.02	0.025	0.03
		Total	0.049	0.0655	0.082
m: effect of channel meandering appreciable	1.35 sinuosity:		1.15	1.15	1.15

Manning n coefficient:

min	mean	max
0.0563	0.0753	0.0943

0.0109

Small-scale meanders (11200-6600 cal. BP)

		N Manning	min	mean	max
n1: surface roughness: (caused by grain size of sediments at channel bottom)	0.2 mm	0.012	0.012	0.012	0.012
n2: effect of vegetation medium (dense vegetation cover in the middle Holocene)		0.01-0.025	0.01	0.0175	0.025
n3: channel irregularity (bars, dunes, ripplemarks) minor (no or rare traces of bedforms in the channel fills)		0.001-0.005	0.001	0.003	0.005
n4: channel alignment gradual variations in channel cross-sections (a regular meandering planform with similar widths and depths of channels)		0	0	0	0
n5: effect of obstructions negligible (a few scattered obstructions: possibly tree stumps in the river bed)		0-0.004	0	0.002	0.004
		Total	0.023	0.0345	0.046
m: effect of channel meandering severe	sinuosity: 2,5		1,3	1,3	1,3

Manning n coefficient:

min	mean	max
0.0299	0.04485	0.0598

0.0086

Sinuuous channels (300 - 200 cal. BP)

		N Manning	min	mean	max
n1: surface roughness:	0.4 mm	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02
n2: effect of vegetation medium (possible presence of vegetation - lack of eroding and reworking of the channel bottoms)		0.01-0.025	0.01	0.0175	0.025
n3: channel irregularity (bars, dunes, ripplemarks) small (no or small traces of bedforms)		0.001-0.005	0.001	0.003	0.005
n4: channel alignment large and small cross-sections alternating occasionally		0.001-0.005	0.001	0.003	0.005
n5: effect of obstructions appreciable (traces of buried objects, possibly buried tree logs, in the channel fills)		0.02-0.03	0.02	0.025	0.03
		Total	0.052	0.0685	0.085
m: effect of channel meandering appreciable	1.09 sinuosity:		1	1	1

Manning n coefficient:

min	mean	max
0.052	0.0685	0.085

0.0095

Sinuuous channels (11200-2800 cal. BP)

n1: surface roughness:	0.2 mm	0.012	0.012	0.012	0.012	
n2: effect of vegetation medium (possible presence of vegetation in the river bed, no traces of eroding and reworking of the channels)		0.01-0.025	0.01	0.0175	0.025	
n3: channel irregularity (bars, dunes, ripplemarks) minor (no traces of bedforms and/or bank erosion)		0.001-0.005	0.001	0.003	0.005	
n4: channel alignment gradual (size and chape of these channels is comparable in all the measured sections)		0	0	0	0	
n5: effect of obstructions negligible (no traces of roots, piers, logs)		0-0.004	0	0.002	0.004	
Total			0.023	0.0345	0.046	
m: effect of channel meandering appreciable	1.23	sinuosity:		1.15	1.15	1.15

Manning n coefficient:

min	mean	max
0.0264	0.0396	0.0529

0.0076

Crevasse channels (4400 - 4100 cal. BP)

		N Manning	min	mean	max	
n1: surface roughness:	0.2 mm	0.012	0.012	0.012	0.012	
n2: effect of vegetation medium (possible presence of vegetation in the river bed, no traces of eroding and reworking of the channels)		0.01-0.025	0.01	0.0175	0.025	
n3: channel irregularity (bars, dunes, ripplemarks) moderate (traces of bedforms in channel fills)		0.006-0.01	0.006	0.008	0.01	
n4: channel alignment large and small cross-sections alternating occassionally		0.001-0.005	0.001	0.003	0.005	
n5: effect of obstructions severe (traces of a dam impeding the flow in one of the channels)		0.04-0.05	0.04	0.045	0.05	
Total			0.069	0.0855	0.102	
m: effect of channel meandering appreciable	1.28	sinuosity:		1.15	1.15	1.15

Manning n coefficient:

min	mean	max
0.0793	0.0983	0.1173

0.0109

Sió River valley (Hungary) - Slowik et al. (2021)

Large-scale meanders (Late Pleniglacial - 18000 cal. BP)

SE (standard error)

		N Manning	min	mean	max
n1: surface roughness: (caused by grain size of sediments at channel bottom)	fine sand (0.2 mm)	0.012	0.012	0.012	0.012
n2: effect of vegetation small (sparse or no in-channel vegetation - no organic channel fill)		0.002-0.01	0.002	0.006	0.01
n3: channel irregularity (bars, dunes, ripplemarks) minor (no traces of bed forms found in channel bottom)		0.001-0.005	0.001	0.003	0.005
n4: channel alignment width of cross-sections alternates occasionally		0.001-0.005	0.001	0.003	0.005
n5: effect of obstructions minor (single buried objects detected in the channel bottom in section 50; fig.11)		0.005-0.015	0.005	0.01	0.015
m: effect of channel meandering severe	> 1.5 sinuosity:		1.3	1.3	1.3
		Total	0.021	0.034	0.047

Manning n coefficient:

min	mean	max
0.0273	0.0442	0.0611

0.0097

Anabranching channels (18000 - 12900 cal. BP)

		N Manning	min	mean	max
n1: surface roughness: (caused by grain size of sediments at channel bottom)	fine sand (0.2 mm)	0.012	0.012	0.012	0.012
n2: effect of vegetation moderate (bars and bedforms suggest the presence of movable bed but in periods of low flows vegetation could have been present in the river bed)		0.01-0.025	0.01	0.0175	0.025
n3: channel irregularity (bars, dunes, ripplemarks) moderate (bed forms appear in the bottom and lateral parts of the channels)		0.006-0.01	0.006	0.008	0.01
n4: channel alignment large and small cross-sections alternating occasionally		0.001-0.005	0.001	0.003	0.005
n5: effect of obstructions minor (a few buried objects were identified in the channel fills)		0.005-0.015	0.005	0.01	0.015
m: effect of channel meandering severe	> 1.5 sinuosity:		1.3	1.3	1.3
		Total	0.034	0.0505	0.067

Manning n coefficient:

min	mean	max
0.0429	0.06565	0.0871

0.0127

Small-scale meanders (12900 - 200 cal. BP)

		N Manning	min	mean	max
n1: surface roughness: (caused by grain size of sediments at channel bottom)	fine sand (0.2 mm)	0.012	0.012	0.012	0.012
n2: effect of vegetation moderate (bars and bedforms suggest the presence of movable bed but in periods of low flows vegetation could have been present in the river bed)		0.01-0.025	0.01	0.0175	0.025
n3: channel irregularity (bars, dunes, ripplemarks) moderate (traces of bedforms and erosional surfaces appear in the channel fills)		0.006-0.01	0.006	0.008	0.01
n4: channel alignment gradual change of channel cross-sections			0	0	0
n5: effect of obstructions negligible (no traces of in-channel objects identified by coring and GPR)		0-0.004	0	0.002	0.004
m: effect of channel meandering severe	>1.5	sinuosity:	1.3	1.3	1.3
		Total	0.028	0.0395	0.051

Manning n coefficient:

min	mean	max
0.0364	0.05135	0.0663

0.0086

Acrement G.J. & Schneider V.R. (1989) Guide for Selecting Manning's roughness coefficients for natural channels and floodplains. US Geological Survey Water-Supply Paper 2339, 1-37.

Table S4. Estimations of paleodischarges conveyed by channels identified in the middle Obra Valley (Poland) and Sió River Valley (Hungary)

The Obra River valley (Poland)

Large-scale meanders (14650 - 11200 cal. BP)

Study site	Section	wetted perimeter P (m)	cross-section Ab (m2)	hydraulic radius R (m)	slope S	Manning n			SE (standard error)	mean velocity (m/s)			SE (standard error)	bankfull discharge (m3/s)			SE (standard error)
						n min	n average	n max		Vmax	V average	Vmin		Qb max	Qb average	Qb min	
Slowik et al.. (2020)	Large-scale meandering channels																
SITE II	5	102.2	175.0	1.71	0.00012	0.0195	0.0299	0.0403	0.006	0.79	0.52	0.38	0.1203	138.2	91.0	66.5	21.04
SITE II	6b	91.2	186.0	2.04	0.00012	0.0195	0.0299	0.0403	0.006	0.89	0.58	0.43	0.1354	165.5	107.9	80.0	25.17
	SE (standard error)		0.1	0.5													

Small-scale meanders (11200 - 6600 cal. BP)

Slowik et al.. (2020)	BEL1a	56.0	59.0	1.05	0.0002	0.0299	0.04485	0.0598	0.0086	0.74	0.5	0.37	0.1084	43.7	29.5	21.8	6.41
	SE (standard error)		0.1	0.5													

Anabranching channels (~11000- 200 cal. BP)

Study site	Section	wetted perimeter P (m)	cross-section Ab (m2)	hydraulic radius R (m)	slope S	Manning n			SE (standard error)	mean velocity (m/s)			SE (standard error)	bankfull discharge (m3/s)			SE (standard error)
						n min	n average	n max		Vmax	V average	Vmin		Qb max	Qb average	Qb min	
Slowik (2013)	11a	22.4	45.5	2.03	0.0002	0.0563	0.0753	0.0943	0.0109	0.39	0.29	0.24	0.0441	17.7	13.2	10.9	1.99
Slowik (2013)	11b	28.4	33.5	1.18	0.0002	0.0563	0.0753	0.0943	0.0109	0.28	0.21	0.16	0.0348	7.9	6.0	4.5	0.98
Slowik (2013)	14a	62.8	40.0	0.64	0.0002	0.0563	0.0753	0.0943	0.0109	0.18	0.14	0.11	0.0203	7.2	5.6	4.4	0.81
Slowik (2013)	14b	49.1	28.5	0.58	0.0002	0.0563	0.0753	0.0943	0.0109	0.17	0.13	0.1	0.0203	4.8	3.7	2.8	0.58
Slowik (2013)	14c	62.8	74.5	1.19	0.0002	0.0563	0.0753	0.0943	0.0109	0.28	0.21	0.17	0.0321	20.9	8.9	12.7	3.54
Slowik (2013)	17a	43.3	27.0	0.62	0.0002	0.0563	0.0753	0.0943	0.0109	0.15	0.11	0.09	0.0176	4.0	3.0	2.4	0.47
Slowik (2013)	17b	42.2	30.0	0.71	0.0002	0.0563	0.0753	0.0943	0.0109	0.2	0.15	0.12	0.0233	6.0	4.5	3.6	0.7
Slowik (2013)	17c	45.5	26.0	0.57	0.0002	0.0563	0.0753	0.0943	0.0109	0.17	0.13	0.1	0.0203	4.4	3.4	2.6	0.52
Slowik (2013)	17d	57.7	38.5	0.67	0.0002	0.0563	0.0753	0.0943	0.0109	0.19	0.14	0.11	0.0233	7.3	5.4	4.2	0.9
	SE (standard error)		0.1	0.5	SE (standard error)			0.026			0.0192	0.0162	2.03			1.08	1.25

Sinuuous channels (300 - 200 cal. BP)

Slowik et al.. (2020)	SITE II	10	28.5	48.2	1.69	0.00026	0.052	0.0685	0.085	0.0095	0.43	0.33	0.26	0.0493	20.7	15.9	12.5	2.37
	SITE II	19	57.2	77.5	1.35	0.00026	0.052	0.0685	0.085	0.0095	0.41	0.31	0.25	0.0467	31.8	24.0	19.4	3.62
	SITE II	6a	42.9	51.0	1.19	0.00026	0.052	0.0685	0.085	0.0095	0.34	0.26	0.21	0.0379	17.3	13.3	10.7	1.92
	SITE IV	8	23.0	45.0	1.95	0.00026	0.052	0.0685	0.085	0.0095	0.48	0.36	0.29	0.0555	21.6	16.2	13.0	2.51
	SE (standard error)		0.1	0.5	SE (standard error)			0.029			0.021	0.0165	3.12			2.31	1.9	

Sinuuous channels (11200 - 2800 cal. BP)

Slowik et al.. (2020)	SITE III	3	98.9	231.0	2.33	0.00004	0.0264	0.0396	0.0529	0.0076	0.41	0.28	0.21	0.0586	94.7	64.7	48.5	13.53
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Crevasse channels (4400 - 4100 cal. BP)

Slowik et al.. (2020)	SITE III	19	52.9	72.0	1.36	0.00008	0.0793	0.0983	0.1173	0.0109	0.14	0.11	0.09	0.0145	10.1	7.9	6.5	1.05
	SITE III	11	31.8	50.5	1.59	0.00008	0.0793	0.0983	0.1173	0.0109	0.15	0.12	0.1	0.0145	7.6	6.1	5.0	0.75
	SITE III	13	35.1	67.3	1.92	0.00008	0.0793	0.0983	0.1173	0.0109	0.17	0.14	0.12	0.0145	6.0	4.9	4.2	0.52
	SE (standard error)		0.1	0.5	SE (standard error)			0.0088			0.0088	0.0088	1.19			0.87	0.67	

The Sió River valley (Hungary)

Large-scale meanders

Section	wetted perimeter	cross-section	hydraulic radius	slope	Manning n				mean velocity (m/s)			SE (standard error)	bankfull discharge (m3/s)			SE (standard error)
	P (m)	Ab (m2)	R (m)	S	n min	n average	n max		Vmax	V average	Vmin		Qb max	Qb average	Qb min	
1	105.6	260	2.46	0.0006	0.0273	0.0442	0.0611	0.0097	1.59	0.98	0.71	0.2603	413.4	254.8	184.6	67.67
Medina-Szedres	89.4	286	3.21	0.0006	0.0273	0.0442	0.0611	0.0097	1.89	1.17	0.85	0.3075	540.5	334.6	243.1	87.94
Sióagard	0.1	0.5														

Anabranching channels

Section	wetted perimeter	cross-section	hydraulic radius	slope	Manning n				mean velocity (m/s)			SE (standard error)	bankfull discharge (m3/s)			SE (standard error)	
	P (m)	Ab (m2)	R (m)	S	n min	n average	n max		Vmax	V average	Vmin		Qb max	Qb average	Qb min		
8	125	155	1.24	0.0004	0.0429	0.06565	0.0871	0.0127	0.53	0.35	0.26	0.0794	82.15	54.2	40.3	12.3	
Medina-Szedres	47.1	44	0.93	0.0004	0.0429	0.06565	0.0871	0.0127	0.44	0.29	0.22	0.0649	19.4	12.8	9.7	2.86	
Medina-Szedres	34	39.5	43	1.09	0.0004	0.0429	0.06565	0.0871	0.0127	0.49	0.32	0.24	0.0737	21.1	13.8	10.3	3.18
Medina-Szedres	34	35.2	65	1.85	0.0004	0.0429	0.06565	0.0871	0.0127	0.7	0.49	0.29	0.1184	45.5	31.8	18.8	7.7
Medina-Szedres	35	130	156	1.2	0.0004	0.0429	0.06565	0.0871	0.0127	0.52	0.34	0.26	0.0769	81.1	53	40.6	11.98
Medina-Szedres	53	79	94	1.19	0.0004	0.0429	0.06565	0.0871	0.0127	0.52	0.34	0.26	0.0769	48.9	32	24.4	7.24
Medina-Szedres	58	88	83	0.94	0.0004	0.0429	0.06565	0.0871	0.0127	0.44	0.29	0.22	0.0649	36.5	24.1	18.3	5.37
Medina-Szedres	63	77	94	1.22	0.0004	0.0429	0.06565	0.0871	0.0127	0.53	0.35	0.26	0.0794	49.8	32.9	24.4	7.46
Medina-Szedres	30	77	90	1.17	0.0004	0.0429	0.06565	0.0871	0.0127	0.52	0.34	0.25	0.0794	46.8	30.6	22.5	7.14
Sióagard	51	126.5	58	0.46	0.0004	0.0429	0.06565	0.0871	0.0127	0.28	0.18	0.14	0.0416	16.2	10.4	8.1	2.41
Sióagard	52	95.2	106	1.11	0.0004	0.0429	0.06565	0.0871	0.0127	0.5	0.33	0.25	0.0737	53.0	35.0	26.5	7.81
SE (standard error)	0.1	0.5						SE (standard error)	0.0299	0.0218	0.0117		6.68	4.4	3.3		

Small-scale meanders

Section	wetted perimeter	cross-section	hydraulic radius	slope	Manning n				mean velocity (m/s)			SE (standard error)	bankfull discharge (m3/s)			SE (standard error)	
	P (m)	Ab (m2)	R (m)	S	n min	n average	n max		Vmax	V average	Vmin		Qb max	Qb average	Qb min		
23a	28	35	1.25	0.0003	0.0364	0.05135	0.0663	0.0086	0.54	0.38	0.29	0.0794	18.9	13.3	10.1	2.57	
Medina-Szedres	19+21	54.8	30	0.55	0.0003	0.0364	0.05135	0.0663	0.0086	0.31	0.22	0.17	0.041	9.3	6.6	5.1	1.23
Medina-Szedres	26	23.8	28	1.18	0.0003	0.0364	0.05135	0.0663	0.0086	0.52	0.37	0.28	0.07	14.6	10.4	7.8	1.98
Medina-Szedres	40	19.8	35	1.77	0.0004	0.0429	0.06565	0.0871	0.0086	0.67	0.48	0.37	0.0876	23.4	16.8	12.9	3.06
Medina-Szedres	42	27.5	61	2.22	0.0004	0.0429	0.06565	0.0871	0.0086	0.79	0.56	0.33	0.1328	48.19	34.2	20.1	8.11
Medina-Szedres	46	21.7	48	2.21	0.0004	0.0429	0.06565	0.0871	0.0086	0.79	0.56	0.33	0.1328	37.9	26.9	15.8	6.38
Medina-Szedres	45	29.3	34	1.16	0.0003	0.0364	0.05135	0.0663	0.0086	0.51	0.36	0.28	0.0674	17.3	12.2	9.5	2.29
Medina-Szedres	40	18.2	18	0.99	0.0003	0.0364	0.05135	0.0663	0.0086	0.46	0.33	0.25	0.0612	8.3	5.9	4.5	1.11
SE (standard error)	0.1	0.5						SE (standard error)	0.0588	0.0417	0.0214		4.96	3.52	1.89		